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**THE BOYARS WHO SIGNED THE OATH
OF ALLEGIANCE ON 12 OCTOBER 1777.
PROSOPOGRAPHICAL NOTES***

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The last public international rights event consecrating – in terms of international political relations – the Ottoman Porte having ceded Bucovina to the Habsburg Empire was the signing in Palamutke on 2 July 1776 the Austro-Turkish Convention on the border of the yielded territory. Following this event, one of the essential questions raised by the Court in Vienna and the Military Administration in Bucovina concerned *the oath of allegiance* to be sworn by the population of the new province to the Habsburg authorities¹. The details of the oath-swearing were laid out in July 1777 by General Gabriel von Spleny (the first administrator of Bucovina) and approved by the General commandment of Galicia a month later – with some amendments². After these decisions, on 27 August 1777, General Spleny addressed a manifesto in the name of Empress Maria Theresia to all the inhabitants of “the Bucovina district”, “all the clergymen and laymen, as well as the entire community, must obey and swear an oath of allegiance to show their loyalty and law-abiding status”³. At the end of September, for a few days, officers and

* The study is based on the paper with the same name presented during the National Congress of the Romanian Historians, Iași, 31 August 2018, within the section titled *Biography, genealogy, prosopography – interpretations, perspectives, hypotheses*.

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¹ Mihai-Ștefan Ceașu, *Bucovina habsburgică. De la anexare la Congresul de la Viena. Iosefinism și postiosefinism. 1775-1815*, Fundația Academică “A. D. Xenopol”, Iași, 1998, p. 70.

² *Ibidem*.

³ *Ibidem*, p. 71.

mazili [boyars without a rank] wandered the towns and villages of the province to obtain the oath of allegiance from inhabitants⁴.

The official oath ceremony took place in Cernăuți on 12 October 1777. Boyar Ilie Herescu uttered it before the commission presided by General Spleny and Bishop Dositei Herescu in the presence of the representatives of privileged estates attending the ceremony, who repeated the oath of allegiance after him. The afore-mentioned bishop, his brother Ilie Herescu *staroste* [prefect] of Cernăuți, Leon Imbault and his son-in-law Iacob Logoteti, Vasile Balș and Peter Nagni, former *ispravnic* [prefect] of Suceava signed the document. The rest of the noblemen and high clergy members signed in the chancellery of the Imperial Administration. Through their gesture, the representatives of the Bucovinian nobiliary estate reasserted their desire to be involved in the political and administrative matters of the new province, according to their privileges and economic position⁵. Fortunately, the names of the signatories have survived to our day; Johann Polek featured their list in a paper published in Cernăuți in 1902⁶. It mentions that the Bucovinian nobiliary estate had 26 boyars, 92 *mazili*, 109 *ruptași* [taxpayers], and 142 *șleahțici* [small boyars] as representatives. The high clergy was represented by the former Moldavian Metropolitan, Iacov (who was tonsured a monk at Putna by the Rădăuți Bishop Dositei Herescu), several archimandrites and protopopes⁷.

Thus, the list published by Johann Polek comprises the names of the most significant representatives of the Bucovinian families, and their prosopographic analyses can reveal numerous aspects regarding the social, political, and cultural context of their time. The objective of this paper is to assess from a prosopographic standpoint the 26 persons who – in the document signed on 12 October 1777 – constituted the group of the most notable Bucovinian nobiliary estates, i.e. the boyars, who seem to be

⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 72-73.

⁶ Johann Polek, *Die Huldigung der Bukowina am 12 Oktober 1777*, in “Jahrbuch des Bukowiner Landes-Museums Zehnter Jahrgang”, editorial committee C. Mandyczwski, A. Mikulicz, dr. J. Polekand, C. A. Romstorfer, Czernowitz, 1902, p. 3-36, a text from which they were republished on p. 7-11 in Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, Mircea-Cristian Ghenghea (coord.), *Pro Bucovina. Repere istorice și naționale*, Biblioteca Națională a României, Bucharest, 2010, p. 351-355 (from which I will cite hereinafter).

⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 351-355.

different from the *mazili*, *ruptași*, and *șleahtici*. The difference resides not so much in their wealth and national seniority but in their local role in the years before the territorial separation, the jobs assigned by the Moldavian princes, and the trust shown to them by the community.

In the order published by Polek, they were as follows: *vornic* [magistrate] Anghelachi, Vasile Balș, Toader Flondor, Ioan Flondor, Ilie Herescu, Toader Herescu, Leon Imbault, Ioan Costin, Ioan Calmuțchi senior, Ioan Calmuțchi junior, Nicolae Gafencu, Vasile Flondor, Ruxandra Știrbățoiaie, Ilie Flondor, Ilie Cârstea, Ianache Codrescu, Iacob Logoteti, Ioan Mitescu, Ioan Strâșca, Vasile Strâșca, Mihalache Giurgiuvan, Dumitrașcu Gafencu, Peter Nagni, Simion Turcul, Vasile Herescu, and Maria Bălșoiaia.

These characters comprise some renowned names identified and set by the Romanian historiography on the branches of their genealogical trees, which I will not further detail here. It is worth noting, in this respect, **Baron Vasile Balș** – well-known for his involvement in the Bucovinian public life and to whom Mihai-Ștefan Ceaușu dedicated an entire book⁸. Not equally emblematic but still quite famous are the boyars of the Flondor family, represented in my list by the brothers Ioan and Toader (the sons of the great *medelnicer* [high ranked servant] Șerban Flondor, a descendant of the brave *armaș* [in charge of carrying out punishments in the prince's name] Toader, the son of Pavel Albotă)⁹. The one bearing his ancestor's name a century later, i.e. **Toader Flondor** (who signed the oath of allegiance in 1777), was married twice to girls from the Stârcea and Samson families, but he had no offsprings¹⁰. His brother **Ioan Flondor**, *vornic* of Câmpulung¹¹, had nine children with his wife Anastasia Arapu¹², four girls (Safta, Alexandra, Anița, and Maria)

⁸ Mihai-Ștefan Ceaușu, *Un illuminist bucovinean: boierul Vasile Balș (1756-1832)*, Junimea, Iași, 2007.

⁹ Sever Zotta, *Obârșia familiei Flondor*, in **AG**, VI (XI), no. 1-4, 1999, p. 1-2 (a paper initially featured in "Bukowiner Heimatblätter", I, no. 1-3, 1933, and published in 1999; translated by Zoe Diaconescu). Concerning the filiation of Flondor and Ciudin from Pavel Albotă, see Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Din lumea cronicarului Ion Neculce. Studiu prosopografic*, foreword by Ștefan S. Gorovei, Editura Universității "Alexandru Ioan Cuza", Iași, 2015, p. 286-287.

¹⁰ Sever Zotta, *op. cit.*, p. 10. His will of 14 June 1786 is summarised in Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, V, Cernăuți, 1939, p. 76 (no. 5).

¹¹ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, V, p. 76 (no. 6).

¹² *Ibidem*, p. 185 (no. 2).

and five boys (Vasile, Dimitrie, Constantin, Gheorghe, and Ioan)¹³. The last five carried the name of their family in numerous branches. Among the children, Vasile is one of the boyars who signed the oath of 1777. **Vasile Flondor**, who became “*obervornic*”¹⁴, had three children – Gheorghe, Constantin, and Dumitrache – to whom he left a good portion of his wealth through the will drafted in Hlinița on 20 July 1819¹⁵. Concerning “Ilie Flondor” – another name in this list – there are no insights (more than likely, a character with this name never existed). As far as we know, until the mid-19th century, the given name Ilie was not mentioned in the onomastic heritage of the Flondor family. Hence, it may be suggested that – behind a transcription error –there was the given name of another son (most probably the homonym of his father, **Ioan Flondor**).

The boyars of the Herescu family, all living in northern parts of Moldavia, are also well-known descendants of Toader Herescu, who lived in the mid-17th century¹⁶. The persons in this list are Ilie and Toader, the brothers of Dositei Herescu, the last Rădăuți bishop and the first Bucovina bishop. **Ilie Herescu**, who became *logofăt de vistierie* [treasurer], *staroste* of Cernăuți, and great *medelnicer*, married Ecaterina (daughter of Gavril Hușanul), and they had five children: Ghenadie the monk, Neculai, Gheorghe, Vasile, and Ileana¹⁷. His brother **Toader Herescu** was also a captain and then the *staroste* of Cernăuți; he had no children¹⁸. The last of the Herești featured in 1777 is **Vasile**, the son of Ilie Herescu, baptised by Metropolitan Iacov Putneanul himself¹⁹. Once he became a great captain, he worked for a while after the province’s annexation as a secretary in the Commission of Consistories in charge of

¹³ *Ibidem*, p. 76 (no. 4).

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, VI, Bucharest, 1942, p. 115 (no. 4); p. 350 (no. 4).

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, V, p. 77 (no. 11).

¹⁶ Ștefan S. Gorovei, *Hereștii*, a paper presented before the Commission of Heraldry, Genealogy, and Sigillography of the Romanian Academy, Iași Branch, on 15 March 2005. See also Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Ctitori ai Sihăstriei Putnei din veacul al XVIII-lea. Note prosopografice*, in **AP**, XIV, no. 1, 2018, p. 299 and 308 (genealogical table).

¹⁷ Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Ctitori ai Sihăstriei Putnei*, p. 300-301.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 300.

¹⁹ Idem, *O danie a lui Iacov Putneanul și semnificațiile ei*, in **AP**, VII, no. 1, 2011, p. 191-204.

assessing the incomes of monasteries²⁰. He seems to have had no children.

Two other persons who signed the 1777 document belong to the Strâșca family – a highly ramified lineage; it is challenging to track down the members due to all the homonymies. In a recently published paper²¹, we managed to untangle the genealogical intertwining of the Bucovinian lineage, among others. Hence, we found out that the persons who signed the oath – Ioniță and his son Vasile – come from a branch that sometime in the past took the name of a girl born Strâșca. It is Maria, the daughter of Vasile Strâșca, who married before 1710 Ștefan the captain, who took his wife's patronym²². His son was called **Ioan Strâșca** – featured in 1777, the most notable representative of the 18th-century family, involved for 50 years in the preservation and increase of the real estate heritage and the public life through his presence in many transactions or decisions regarding estate limits. In 1739-1755, he was attested as a second *paharnic*²³ [cupbearer] and a great captain²⁴. He was married to a girl of the Samson family, and they had a son called **Vasile Strâșca**²⁵, who also signed the 1777 document. Following the annexation of Bucovina, Vasile signed some records as a second *paharnic*²⁶ but is attested only a few

²⁰ *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean. Catalog de documente (1393-1849)*, drafted by Vasile Gh. Miron, Mihai-Ștefan Ceașu, Gavril Irimescu, Sevastița Irimescu, Direcția Generală a Arhivelor Statului, Bucharest, 1983, p. 457, no. 1377.

²¹ Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Genealogii bucovinene din veacul al XVIII-lea: familiile Turculeț și Strâșca*, in Cristian Ploscaru (ed.), *Elita românească și itinerariile modernității. Omagiu Profesorului Mihai Cojocariu*, Editura Universității “Alexandru Ioan Cuza”, Iași, 2021, p. 55-70, p. 69 (genealogical table).

²² *Ibidem*, p. 62-65.

²³ See for instance the documents issued on 12 July 1739 (Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, IV, Cernăuți, 1938, p. 159-160; 20 December 1741 (*ibidem*, p. 160); 15 July 1742 (*ibidem*, p. 122-123); 3 August 1746 (*ibidem*, V, p. 10-11, no. 7); 18 January 1748 (*ibidem*, III, Cernăuți, 1937, p. 50); 3 May 1750 (*ibidem*, V, p. 57-58, no. 33); 8 July 1751 (*ibidem*, p. 72, no. 43) or 7 July 1755 (*ibidem*, p. 11).

²⁴ Attested by numerous documents, among which I mention here those issued on 2 December 1759 (*ibidem*, IV, p. 122-123), 20 June 1760 (*ibidem*, p. 163), 10 August 1762 (*ibidem*, p. 169), 16 July 1763 (*ibidem*, III, p. 37), 25 May 1765 (*ibidem*, VI, p. 140, no. 46), 17 May 1767 (*ibidem*, III, p. 50-51), 5 May 1772 (*ibidem*, VI, p. 81-82), 9 July 1773 (*ibidem*, p. 306), 25 June 1775 (*ibidem*, p. 185), 30 July 1784 (*ibidem*, p. 271), or 9 October 1788 (*ibidem*, IV, p. 215-216).

²⁵ Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Genealogii bucovinene*, p. 65 and footnote 114.

²⁶ See the documents issued on 2 September 1782 (Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 263), 6 July 1792 (*ibidem*, p. 349) or 8 January 1797 (*ibidem*, p. 264).

times. He was married to a certain Catrina, who gave him seven children: Ruxandra, Nastasia, married to Ștefan Vasilco, Maria, the lady of Nicolae Butuce, Ilinca, the wife of Petre Vlahovici, Anița married to a certain Gheorghe Flondor, Dumitraș, and Toderăș. Vasile Strășca died before 15 March 1810²⁷.

A lineage we have recently studied²⁸ is the one Simion Turcul belongs to; he is another boyar who signed the 1777 document. The root of his family goes back to the 15th century, and the most illustrious of his ascendants was beyond doubt his grandfather, *rohmistru* [cavalry captain] Constantin Turculeț, who joined in the late 17th century the military service of the Polish crown and whose reputation of bravery got to the Ottoman sultan's ears²⁹. Throughout his life, Constantin (Costașco) Turculeț gathered a significant number of villages in the districts at the northern limit of Moldavia, all found in the descendants' heritage even more than a century later. Simion Turcul, our character, was the son of *postelnic* [chamberlain] Gheorghe and the grandson of the *rohmistru*³⁰. He is a rare find in the sources, particularly given that the Habsburg authorities – at the beginning of the ninth decade of the 18th century – received statements concerning the owners of the villages in the annexed territory³¹. He had no offspring; confirmed by the documents of 27 December 1811, the Court of Cernăuți ruled that all the estates in Bucovina of the late Simion Turcul should be transferred to the property of his cousin Tadeus Turcul³².

Among the signatory parties we find (which is no coincidence) Costin, **Ioan Costin** of Șipeniț, the son of Miron nicknamed Mutenco. With old roots in the Moldavian realm, a descendant of the *logofăt* [chancellor] Miron Costin and his wife, lady Ileana Movilă³³, Ioan Costin Mutenco was married to a certain Ilinca, and their children were Iordache *postelnic* and Maria, married to Alexandru Jian³⁴. Not many details are known about the public activity of this character, but his presence in the

²⁷ Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Genealogii bucovinene*, p. 65 and footnote 114.

²⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 56-63; p. 68 (genealogical table).

²⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 57-59.

³⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 60-61.

³¹ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 220-221.

³² Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Genealogii bucovinene*, p. 61 and footnote 71.

³³ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 310-311, no. 103.

³⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 311-312 (no. 1-7). See also Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Din lumea cronicarului Ion Neculce*, p. 329-330, p. 566 (genealogical table).

Bucovinian boyars list is definitely due to his illustrious ascendance. For the same reason, the two ladies **Ruxandra Știrbățoia** and Maria Bălșoia must have been featured. The first was the descendant of the Balș lineage, the daughter of the second *logofăt* Vasile Balș³⁵. Ruxandra, living in the estates in the north of the country, was first married to *jitnicer* [in charge of the princely grain warehouses] Nicolae Cucoranu and then Nicolae Știrbăț, whose name he bore in 1777³⁶. The second lady, **Maria Bălșoia**, was the daughter of Toader Cantacuzino³⁷, a first cousin of the Deleni who ruled Moldavia in that period. She was married to Vasile Balș, the nephew of Ruxandra Știrbățoia, and they had three children: Toader, Toma, and Safta³⁸.

Except for these characters, whom we identified quickly, there are three others about whom the documents are relatively scarce in terms of information. Not coincidentally, the three individuals do not have Moldavian roots, but all of them have connected their destinies to the territories annexed by the imperials. About **Peter Nagni**, we only know he was, for a while, the *ispravnic* of Suceava³⁹; as for the other two, Leon Imbault and Giacomo Logoteti, they were mentioned by Teodor Balan, who accessed the personal archive of their descendants. **Leon Imbault** (L'Imbault, Limbo, Imbo) had French origins, but he was born in Greece (Acarmania) and raised and educated in a monastery of Pera. In 1733, he joined the service of the French embassy in Constantinople; then, he became a dragoman in Crete and Morena. In Moldavia, he arrived in 1745, but he is attested as a diplomatic agent of Prince Grigore Calimah as late as 1768⁴⁰. He decided to settle in Moldavia, where he was appointed great *paharnic*⁴¹. Following several real estate exchanges with

³⁵ Mihai Dim. Sturdza, *Familia Balș*, in Idem (ed.), *Familiele boierești din Moldova și Țara Românească. Enciclopedie istorică, genealogică și biografică*, vol. I (Abaza-Bogdan), Simetria, Bucharest, 2004, p. 251 (genealogical table).

³⁶ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, V, p. 209-210 (no. 1).

³⁷ Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Din lumea cronicarului Ion Neculce*, p. 236 and footnote 6, p. 558 (genealogical table).

³⁸ Mihai Dim. Sturdza, *Familia Balș*, p. 252-253 (genealogical table). See also Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, III, p. 192 (no. 1).

³⁹ *Suceava, file de istorie. Documente privitoare la istoria orașului (1388-1918)*, vol. I, drafted by Vasile Gh. Miron, Mihai-Ștefan Ceașu, Ioan Caproșu, Gavril Irimescu, Direcția Generală a Arhivelor Statului, Bucharest, 1989, p. 447-448, no. 290.

⁴⁰ Teodor Balan, *Moșia Cernauca și familia Hurmuzachi*, excerpt from "Anuarul Liceului «Aron Pumnul»", 1923/24, Cernăuți, 1925, p. 10.

⁴¹ Idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 230, no. 80.

the Monastery of St. Spiridon, he became the owner of the Șerăuți and Bănila estates in the district of Cernăuți⁴², where he moved indefinitely (he was appointed *staroste*). In this capacity, he was summoned by the prince in Iași and then by the Austrian authorities to rule on matters⁴³ or decide on property limits⁴⁴. He married Adriana, born Wuzin⁴⁵, who gave him one child: Ecaterina (Catarina), who married Count Giacomo Logoteti⁴⁶ on 6 August 1775. Leon Imbault drafted his will in Cernăuți on 19 February 1781⁴⁷, and he died a few weeks later, before 31 March⁴⁸. His son-in-law, **Giacomo (Iacob) Logoteti**, also a signatory party of the oath, had a dubious and tangled past before his arrival to Moldavia. According to the documents he submitted to Austrian authorities, his ascendants were Constantinople inhabitants before the Ottoman conquest. Still, after 1453, they wandered around the Mediterranean Sea islands until they joined the Venetian services. Iacob was the son of Giorgio Logoteti, and he was born on Zante Island on 16 March 1741. He also joined the Venetian services, which he left in a hurry after falsifying documents (an offence for which he was sentenced to death in absentia and hanged in effigy in Corfu). He wandered through Europe for a while, mostly Petersburg, where he made a series of debts⁴⁹. Fleeing creditors, he settled in Moldavia at Șerăuți, where he married the only daughter of Leon Imbault, thus inheriting his entire wealth. Catarina gave him six children: Leon, Iosif, Alois, Francisc, Maria, and Susanna⁵⁰. Iacob died on 10 October 1802, and he was buried at Șerăuți⁵¹.

The prosopographic analysis of the nine persons left within the list of the boyars who signed the documents of 12 October 1777 has never been published before.

⁴² Idem, *Moșia Cernauca*, p. 10.

⁴³ See the documents issued on 5 May 1772 (idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 81-82) or 25 June 1775 (*ibidem*, p. 185).

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*, V, p. 202.

⁴⁵ *Ibidem*, VIII, edited by Ioan Caproșu, index by Arcadie Bodale, Editura Taida, Iași, 2006, p. 103.

⁴⁶ Idem, *Moșia Cernauca*, p. 10.

⁴⁷ Idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VIII, p. 102-103, no. 104.

⁴⁸ *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 441, no. 1332.

⁴⁹ Teodor Balan, *Moșia Cernauca*, p. 8-10.

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 10. For all of them see idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 284-287 (no. 1-7).

⁵¹ Idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VIII, p. 121.

The first of them (and the first of the 1777 list) was *vornic* [Vasile] Anghelachi. Attested as a *vornic* of Botoșani and judge between 1770 and 1789⁵², Anghelache is the direct descendant of Cârstea Brăileanu, who lived in the mid-17th-century⁵³. Whereas I was not able to track down the precise family genealogy, Cârstea Brăileanu's lineage may be reconstructed by following the sequence of ownership of the Ruși village (Botoșani district). One of Brăileanu's sons was named Anghelache⁵⁴, and the given name later became a patronym. This Anghelache married Cristina, the daughter of Simion Mihăilescu⁵⁵. He inherited a part of the Ruși village from his parents, confirmed on 1 January 1678⁵⁶ and 6 July 1680⁵⁷. On 28 February 1707⁵⁸ and 12 August 1719⁵⁹, a certain Gavril Anghelache, a local free villager (most probably the son of the preceding one), witnessed the sales of a part of Ruși. On 23 June 1747⁶⁰ and 22 August 1766⁶¹, Ioan Anghelache (Gavril's descendant) was an "estate owner" and witnessed when some of the village's limits were established. This Ioan must have been our character's father. The *vornic* who signed the 1777 document had the given name Vasile⁶²; we know that on 2 August 1789, he was still alive⁶³. He had a daughter Maria, married to Toader Goian, who, on 18 June 1795, left his children Iordache and Catrina several village sections,

⁵² *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 443, no. 1338; p. 474, no. 1435; Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 304-305.

⁵³ CDM, III, drafted by Mihai Regleanu, Doina Duca, Constanța Negulescu, Veronica Vasilescu, Cornelia Crivăț, Direcția Generală a Arhivelor Statului, Bucharest, 1968, p. 321, no. 1487.

⁵⁴ N. Iorga, *Studii și documente cu privire la istoria românilor*, V, Bucharest, 1903, p. 224, no. 53 (hereinafter: N. Iorga, *Studii și documente*).

⁵⁵ CDM, III, p. 321, no. 1487; p. 351, no. 1636; *ibidem*, suppl. I, drafted by Maria Soveja, Mihai Regleanu, Doina Tincușcu, Marcel Ciuca, Gabriela Birceanu, Direcția Generală a Arhivelor Statului, Bucharest, 1975, p. 294, no. 917.

⁵⁶ N. Iorga, *Studii și documente*, V, p. 224, no. 53.

⁵⁷ *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 196, no. 587.

⁵⁸ N. Iorga, *Studii și documente*, V, p. 227-228, no. 65.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 230, no. 74.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 245, no. 112.

⁶¹ *Ibidem*, p. 253-254, no. 138.

⁶² Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 274-275.

⁶³ *Ibidem*, p. 304-305.

among which those of Ruși (near Botoșani), a dowry from the late Vasile Anghelache⁶⁴.

Two other characters – father and son – were the representatives of the Calmuțchi family. The oldest ascendant of this lineage was Ian (Ioan) Calmuțchi, who – as a reward for his military services in Poland – was made a noble by John Sobieski, as proven by a diploma dated 4 February 1676⁶⁵. He had two sons: Dumitraș, great captain⁶⁶ and Gheorghe, great *comis* [in charge of the princely horses and stables], both with many descendants. The latter married Ileana, the daughter of *șetrar* [in charge of camp tents during the war] Constantin Pârvu⁶⁷, with whom he had numerous boys and girls. Among them, we note **Ioan Calmuțchi senior**, one of the signatory parties of the oath. On 20 June 1766, his maternal uncle Vasile Pârvu, “noting that he was a kind, pious, and God-fearing child”, gave him a part of his wealth, which included some of the Călinești estate (Cernăuți district) particularly, with its house and goods, to manage them until his death⁶⁸. He had inherited another part of Călinești from his father; thus, Ioan Calmuțchi lived there his entire life. He was a captain and – after the annexation of the north – in 1781-1783, he was an assessor and a member of the commission that established the Bucovinian estate limits⁶⁹. Until the last decade of the 18th century, Ioan Calmuțchi is often mentioned in documents because he decided on limits⁷⁰, drafted documents⁷¹, and bore witness to various transactions⁷².

⁶⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 274-275.

⁶⁵ Andi-Marius Dașchievici, *Diploma de indigenat polon a familiei Kalmuski*, in **AG**, VII (XII), no. 1-2, 2000, p. 123-128.

⁶⁶ Regarding him, see the documents issued on 5 October 1710 (Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, III, p. 157-158, no. 124), 23 November 1711 (*ibidem*, p. 162-163, no. 128), 10 January 1712 (*ibidem*, p. 164-165, no. 130), 25 October 1717 (*ibidem*, p. 187-188, no. 151) or 18 January 1727 (*ibidem*, IV, p. 68-69, no. 45). Dumitraș married Agafia (*ibidem*, III, p. 165) and had Nicolae (tonsured as a monk as Natanail) (*ibidem*, V, p. 73) and Mihalache, with a rich lineage (*ibidem*, p. 56-57; p. 73-74).

⁶⁷ *Ibidem*, IV, p. 196-197, no. 129.

⁶⁸ *Ibidem*, VI, p. 169-172, no. 59.

⁶⁹ *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 446, no. 1349; p. 447, no. 1350; p. 447-448, no. 1351; p. 449, no. 1353; p. 450, no. 1355; p. 454, no. 1365; p. 458-459, no. 1385; p. 468-469, no. 1418; p. 469, no. 1419; p. 469-470, no. 1420.

⁷⁰ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VIII, p. 115-117, no. 120.

⁷¹ Idem, *Familia Onciul. Studiu și documente*, Cernăuți, 1927, p. 124-126, no. 103; p. 132-133, no. 110; idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 240 (no. 6).

⁷² Idem, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 130 (no. 11); p. 317 (no. 2).

He married Ilinca, the daughter of Ioan Miteșcu, whose dowry included village parts in the Dorohoi, Suceava, and Cernăuți districts⁷³. Ioan Calmuțchi wrote his will at Călinești on 14 February 1797, which shows that he had ten children: three daughters (Zoița, one married to Costache Flondor, and another to Dumitraș Costin) and seven boys (Nicolae, Constantin, Ștefan, Vasile, Gheorghe, Mihalache, and Ioan)⁷⁴. He died before 9 February 1798, when his wife was mentioned in documents as a widow⁷⁵. One of his children, **Ioan Calmuțchi junior**, was among the 1777 signatory parties. He is featured rather scarcely in the papers until late 1807⁷⁶.

Two other oath signatories belonged to the Gafencu family. They are brothers Nicolae and Dumitrașcu, the sons of *uricar* [in charge of drafting princely documents] Miron Gafencu and one of Alexandru Ilschi⁷⁷. In 1754, following their father's death, Nicolae and Dumitrașcu divided between them the inheritance that comprised parts of villages in the Cernăuți district⁷⁸. **Nicolae Gafencu** was *vornic* of Câmpulung Rusc for a long time; he often went to the country's northern districts to rule on estate parts or accomplish various princely duties⁷⁹. He died in his childhood village of Bănila before 23 May 1793, when his wife Nastasia decided on the inheritance with the sons of their two children, Andrei and Vasile⁸⁰. His brother, **Dumitrașcu Gafencu**, signed his life as a second

⁷³ *Ibidem*, p. 188 (no. 1).

⁷⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 172 (no. 1).

⁷⁵ *Idem*, *Familia Onciul*, p. 172, no. 146.

⁷⁶ *Idem*, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 368 (no. 9). Not to be mistaken for his homonym within the branch of Berbești, also in the Cernăuți district (*ibidem*, p. 394).

⁷⁷ For Miron Gafencu's life and activity, see Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, "*Bucuroși muscalilor și greșiți prea luminatei Porți*". *Oamenii măriei sale Dumitrașcu vodă Cantemir, pribegi la Harkov*, in Cristian Ploscaru, Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu (eds.), *Elitele puterii – puterea elitelor în spațiul românesc (secolele XV-XX)*, Editura Universității "Alexandru Ioan Cuza", Iași, 2018, p. 252-254.

⁷⁸ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VIII, p. 20-23, no. 23.

⁷⁹ See the documents issued on 16 May 1755 (*ibidem*, V, p. 42-43), 20 July 1758 (Arhivele Naționale ale României, Colecția "Achiziții noi", chronological index no. 25, vol. II, drafted by Marcel-Dumitru Ciucă, Silvia Vătafu-Găitan, Mirela Comănescu, Laura Niculescu, Arhivele Naționale ale României, Bucharest, 2008, p. 256, no. 2841); 22 July 1761 (Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 24-26, no. 8); 25 May 1765 (*ibidem*, p. 140, no. 46); 15 March 1783 (*ibidem*, p. 42).

⁸⁰ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, V, p. 39 (no. 12). For Nicolae Gafencu's posterity, see also *ibidem*, p. 100 (no. 9); *ibidem*, VI, p. 115 (no. 4); p. 335 (no. 7).

stolnic [high steward]⁸¹. He had no offsprings, so he left all his wealth to two nephews (through sales and donations)⁸².

The ascendancy of **Ilie Cârste**'s family (another signatory party of the 1777 oath) is stated and confirmed by the document issued on 25 August 1773 by the boyars within the Moldavian Duchy Divan. Thus, the oldest known forefather of the family was *căminar* [collector of duties on spirits] Cârste, who lived in the mid-17th-century. His son, great *jitnicer* Toader Cârste had Iordache Cârste, the great captain of Dorohoi. The last married Maria, one of Ioan Abaza's daughters, and had Ioan and Ilie Cârste as sons; the latter is our 1777 character⁸³. Ilie is mentioned as early as 1756 in litigation for the parental estates within the Suceava district, among which Costâna (his courts were there)⁸⁴. In the documents attesting to his numerous tasks in the area, he was often sent to establish limits⁸⁵ or rule on matters⁸⁶. Ilie signed until his death as a *șetrar* or former great *șetrar*, a task attributed by the Iași princes around 1765⁸⁷. From 1775 to 1782, Ilie Cârste was also the *ispravnic* [prefect] of the Suceava district⁸⁸. With support from Bishop Dositei Herescu, in 1782, Ilie Cârste founded in Suceava a school on the site of St. Dimitrie Church, an institution that must have functioned until around 1817⁸⁹. He married Nastasia, the daughter of Mihalache Cheșco⁹⁰, and they had two girls (Caterina and Ileana) and three boys (Barons Toader, Gheorghe, and Ioan von Cârste)⁹¹. Ilie died on 5 March 1798⁹² and was probably buried in the family church of Costâna.

⁸¹ *Ibidem*, V, p. 37 (no. 3).

⁸² *Ibidem*, VI, p. 335 (no. 6).

⁸³ *Ibidem*, p. 252 (no. 1).

⁸⁴ *Ibidem*, V, p. 43-44, no. 22; p. 131, no. 71; p. 199, no. 102.

⁸⁵ *Ibidem*, III, p. 25; *ibidem*, V, p. 93; p. 143.

⁸⁶ *Ibidem*, V, p. 176.

⁸⁷ Ilie Cârste is attested as a *șetrar* and former great *șetrar* in documents such as those issued on 5 July 1768 (*ibidem*, III, p. 25), 2 November 1771 (*ibidem*, V, p. 93), 3 January 1776 (*ibidem*, VI, p. 96-97) or 18 August 1776 (*ibidem*, V, p. 143).

⁸⁸ See, for instance, the documents dated 3 June 1777 (*ibidem*, p. VIII, p. 94-95, no. 96), 6 January 1779 (*ibidem*, V, p. 176), 23 January 1782 (*ibidem*, p. 117), 11 December 1782 (*ibidem*, p. 190-191).

⁸⁹ *Suceava, file de istorie*, p. 606-617, no. 370.

⁹⁰ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 97 (no. 3); p. 276-277 (no. 10).

⁹¹ *Ibidem*, V, p. 136 (no. 4).

⁹² *Ibidem*.

Enache Codrescu came to Bucovina relatively late; by all appearances, he never owned anything here. His inclusion among the boyars who signed the 1777 document may be due to his qualities and, perhaps, his relations in Iași (where he had spent his childhood). His grandfather, Andrei Codrescu, owned a part of the Codrești estate in the Cârlișău district (his son Ioan inherited the village)⁹³. He became the second *medelnicer* and raised his eight or nine children in Iași⁹⁴. His testament provisions dated 28 February 1770 show that his son Enache had been a burden to the family, for he had spent more than earning in his jobs⁹⁵. Disinherited by his father, Enache – after 1770 – changed gear towards businesses in the northern part of the country, where he leased and managed several villages belonging to the St. Spiridon Monastery⁹⁶. He was there when the Habsburg domination began, and Enache proved helpful to the new authorities, as he was (for a while) a member of the consistory commission in charge of assessing the incomes of monasteries⁹⁷. In the time documents, he signed as a *postelnic*⁹⁸, *pitar*⁹⁹, and *stolnic*¹⁰⁰. On 25 February 1799, he was still alive¹⁰¹; from what I could gather, he was never married.

Ioan Mitescu, another boyar on this list, is the descendant of an old Bucovinian family. His great-grandfather, who lived in the second half of the 17th century, was called Pavel Mitescu, while his grandfather was Gavril¹⁰². His parents were Gheorghe Mitescu and Ioana, the daughter of *armaș* Toader Holban¹⁰³. Ioan Mitescu was a captain his entire life; he was always involved in the daily matters of the Bucovinian

⁹³ *Documente privitoare la istoria orașului Iași*, VI, edited by Ioan Caproșu, Editura “Dosoftei”, Iași, 2004, p. 139, no. 159 (hereinafter: *Documente Iași*).

⁹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 758-760, no. 867

⁹⁵ *Ibidem*.

⁹⁶ *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 438, no. 1319.

⁹⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 457, no. 1377, p. 458, no. 1383.

⁹⁸ *Ibidem*.

⁹⁹ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VIII, p. 599-602, no. 471; *Documente Iași*, IX, edited by Ioan Caproșu, Editura “Dosoftei”, Iași, 2007, p. 2-5, no. 3; p. 23-25, no. 21; p. 35-39, no. 39.

¹⁰⁰ *Documente Iași*, IX, p. 123-125, no. 133; *ibidem*, X, edited by Ioan Caproșu, Editura “Dosoftei”, Iași, 2007, p. 67-73, no. 71.

¹⁰¹ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 408-410, no. 137.

¹⁰² *Ibidem*, p. 15 (no. 3).

¹⁰³ *Ibidem*.

life; he bought or fought for parts of estates¹⁰⁴, he established estate limits¹⁰⁵ or acted as a *vechil* [steward] of the boyars who remained on the other side of the Cordon, in Moldavia¹⁰⁶. He married Casandra, the daughter of Vasile Drăghinici, a granddaughter of former Metropolitan Antonie¹⁰⁷. Only one of his children survived to adulthood, i.e. Ilinca, who married captain Ioan Calmuțchi¹⁰⁸ – whom we described above; on 25 August 1785, Ioan Miteșcu gave her all his village parts in the Dorohoi, Suceava, and Cernăuți districts¹⁰⁹. He died on 14 February 1797¹¹⁰.

Mihalache Giurgiuvan, another signatory party of the 1777 oath, was one of the children born into the family of Dănilă Giurgiuvan and Maria, the daughter of Gheorghe Moțoc¹¹¹. He is attested for the first time in his father's will of 1759 when he received several village parts in the Cernăuți district; his courts were in the Ciortoria estate¹¹². Mihalache signed for a while as the *vornic* of Câmpulung, and he is often mentioned in the documents of the second half of the 18th century¹¹³. He married Maria, the daughter of Ioniță Potlog¹¹⁴, and they had Alexandru¹¹⁵, Matei, Dumitrache, Gheorghe, and Măriuca (Marghiolița) – the wife of Anton Capri¹¹⁶. In a very challenging moment of his life, on 24 June 1795, Mihalache drafted his will¹¹⁷, but he survived until the first years of the

¹⁰⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 14 (no. 1); p. 158-160 (no. 2-3); *ibidem*, V, p. 206 (no. 5).

¹⁰⁵ *Ibidem*, VIII, p. 88-89, no. 89; *ibidem*, IV, p. 32 (no. 3).

¹⁰⁶ See, for instance, the document of 12 May 1782, where Ioan Miteșcu pleaded before the Austrian Commission as Nicolae Ruset's steward (*ibidem*, VI, p. 164). On 29 June 1782, he was in the same position as Vasile Neculce's steward (*ibidem*, V, p. 87).

¹⁰⁷ *Ibidem*, VI, p. 188 (no. 1).

¹⁰⁸ *Ibidem*. See also *Din tezaurul documentar sucevean*, p. 492, no. 1498.

¹⁰⁹ Teodor Balan, *Documente bucovinene*, VI, p. 15 (no. 3).

¹¹⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 172 (no. 1).

¹¹¹ *Ibidem*, IV, p. 22, no. 14; p. 92, no. 65.

¹¹² *Ibidem*, V, p. 188-189, no. 98.

¹¹³ *Ibidem*, p. 33-34 (no. 1); *ibidem*, VI, p. 114-115 (no. 3); p. 137 (no. 4); p. 240 (no. 6); p. 349 (no. 2).

¹¹⁴ See Mihalache Giurgiuvan's first will drafted on 24 June 1795 (*ibidem*, V, p. 189-190).

¹¹⁵ Alexandru, who died before 1795, is not featured in his father's will. Apparently, his godmother was his paternal grandmother, Gafița (Grigore Cracalie's wife) (*ibidem*, VI, p. 65).

¹¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 368 (no. 9).

¹¹⁷ *Ibidem*, V, p. 189-190 (no. 1).

19th century when – before his death on 26 November 1803 – he changed his will¹¹⁸.

However petty we may consider these provincial officials who had long lost their hope to obtain significant state positions, it must not be forgotten that they were notable in their local communities, where they lived (on the outskirts of the principality and then the Empire). They were literate and based on their reports borders were established, and official documents were drafted; they founded churches, made donations, and drafted dowry reports and wills. Above all, though, they were landowners – all the other elements would not have been possible without this capacity. By swearing the oath of allegiance to the House of Habsburg, the political representatives of the population within the annexed territory saw the guarantee of a solemn oath made by the new Christian ruler to observe their domestic autonomy, the country's laws and customs, which never became a reality, however.

**THE BOYARS WHO SIGNED THE OATH
OF ALLEGIANCE ON 12 OCTOBER 1777.
PROSOPOGRAPHICAL NOTES**

Abstract

In Cernăuți in 1902, Johann Polek published a long list of the persons who – on 12 October 1777 – signed the oath of allegiance to Empress Maria Theresia and her co-regent Joseph II. Among them were numerous Moldavians who had joined the Austrian nobility ranks, i.e., 26 *boyars*, 92 *mazili*, 109 *ruptași*, and 142 *șleahtici*. Hence, in my opinion, shortly after Bucovina's annexation by the Habsburg Empire, the Bucovinian nobiliary estates reasserted, through its representatives, the desire to be involved in the political and administrative matter of the new province, in conformity with their privileges and economic position. By using the methodological tools made available by the auxiliary historical sciences, particularly genealogy and prosopography, in this study, I identified them (based on documentary sources). I even reconstructed, when it was possible, the life and activity of the 26 boyars who signed the 1777 document: vornic Anghelachi, Vasile Balș, Toader Flondor, Ioan Flondor, Ioan

¹¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 190.

[Ilie] Herescu, Toader Herescu, Leon Imbault, Ioan Costin, Ioan Calmuțchi senior, Ioan Calmuțchi junior, Nicolae Gafencu, Vasile Flondor, Ruxandra Știrbățoaie, Ilie Flondor, Ilie Cârstea, Ianache Codrescu, Iacob Logoteti, Ioan Mîtescu, Ioan Strâșca, Vasile Strâșca, Mihalache Giurgiuvan, Dumitrașcu Gafencu, Peter Nagni, Simion Turcul, Vasile Herescu, and Maria Bălșoaia. The main objective of this scientific endeavour was to reconstruct the political, social, and cultural profile of the persons for whom the occupation authorities recognised the most significant nobiliary rank of the new province.

Keywords: Moldavia, Bucovinian nobility, Habsburg Bucovina, genealogy, prosopography, 18th century.

ABREVIERI

AARMSI	= Analele Academiei Române. Memoriile Secțiunii Istorice
AARMSL	= Analele Academiei Române. Memoriile Secțiunii Literare
AG	= Arhiva Genealogică
AGR	= Arhiva Genealogică Română
AIIAC	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie și Arheologie, Cluj
AIIAI	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie și Arheologie „A. D. Xenopol”, Iași
AIINC	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie Națională din Cluj
AIIIX	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „A. D. Xenopol”, Iași
AIRCRUV	= Annuario dell’Istituto Romeno di Cultura e Ricerca Umanistica di Venezia
ALIL	= Anuarul de Lingvistică și Istorie Literară, Iași
AM	= Arheologia Moldovei
AMM	= Acta Moldaviae Meridionalis (Vaslui)
AMN	= Acta Musei Napocensis
ANI	= Serviciul Județean al Arhivelor Naționale Iași
ANIC	= Arhivele Naționale Istorice Centrale
AnB	= Analele Brăilei
AnD	= Analele Dobrogei
AnM	= Analele Moldovei
AO	= Arhivele Olteniei
AP	= Analele Putnei
APH	= Acta Poloniae Historica
AR	= Arhiva Românească
ARBSH	= Académie Roumaine. Bulletin de la Section Historique
AȘUI	= Analele Științifice ale Universității „Alexandru I. Cuza”, Iași
AUBI	= Analele Universității București. Seria Istorie
AUI	= Analele Universității Iași. Seria Istorice
BAIESEE	= Bulletin de l’Association Internationale d’Etudes du Sud-Est Européen
BAR	= Biblioteca Academiei Române
BBRF	= Buletinul Bibliotecii Române din Freiburg
BCI	= BCIR
BCIR	= Buletinul Comisiei Istorice a României
BCMI	= Buletinul Comisiunii Monumentelor Istorice
BF	= Byzantinische Forschungen

BMI	= Buletinul Monumentelor Istorice
BN	= Biblioteca Națională a României
BOR	= Biserica Ortodoxă Română
BRV	= Bibliografia Română Veche
BS	= Byzantinoslavica
BSt	= Balkan Studies (Thesaloniki)
BSH. BSHAR	= ARBSH
BSGR	= Buletinul Societății Geografice Române
BSNR	= Buletinul Societății Numismatice Române
BSOAS	= Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies
BZ	= Byzantinische Zeitschrift
CDM	= Catalogul documentelor moldovenești din arhiva istorică centrală a Statului, vol. I-V, București, 1957-1975
CI	= Cercetări Istorice
CL	= Cercetări Literare
Cv. L	= Convorbiri Literare
CMRS	= Cahiers du Monde Russe et Soviétique
CN	= Cercetări Numismatice
CNA	= Cronica Numismatică și Arheologică
DIR	= Documente privind Istoria României (seria A : Moldova; seria B : Țara Românească; seria C : Transilvania)
DOP	= Dumbarton Oaks Papers
DR	= Dacoromania
DRH	= Documenta Romaniae Historica (seria A : Moldova; seria B : Țara Românească; seria C : Transilvania; seria D : Relații între țările române)
EB	= Etudes Balcaniques, Paris
EDr	= Ephemeris Daco-romana
EBPB	= Etudes Byzantines et Post Byzantines
FHDR	= Fontes Historiae Dacoromanae
GB	= Glasul Bisericii
Hurmuzaki, <i>Documente</i>	= Eudoxiu de Hurmuzaki (și colaboratorii), <i>Documente privind istoria românilor</i>
HU	= Historia Urbana
HY	= Historical Yearbook
IN	= Ioan Neculce. Buletinul Muzeului Municipal Iași
LAR	= Literatura și Arta Română
LL	= Limbă și Literatură
LR	= Literatura Română
MA	= Mitropolia Ardealului
MB	= Mitropolia Banatului
MCA	= Materiale și Cercetări Arheologice

MI	= Magazin Istoric
MMS	= Mitropolia Moldovei și Sucevei
MO	= Mitropolia Olteniei
NEH	= Nouvelles Études d'Histoire
OCP	= Orientalia Christiana Periodica
RA	= Revista Arhivelor
RC	= Revista Catolică
RCr.	= Revista Critică
REB	= Revue des Études Byzantines
REG	= Revue des Études Grecques
REI	= Revue des Études Islamiques
RER	= Revue des Études Roumaines
RES	= Revue des Études Slaves
RESEE	= Revue des Études Sud-Est Européennes
RH	= Revue Historique
RHSEE	= Revue Historique du Sud-Est Européen
RdI	= Revista de Istorie
RI	= Revista Istorică (ambele serii)
RIAF	= Revista pentru Istorie, Arheologie și Filologie
RIM	= Revista de Istorie Militară
RIR	= Revista Istorică Română
RIS	= Revista de Istorie Socială
RITL	= Revista de Istorie și Teorie Literară
RM	= Revista Muzeelor
RMM	= Revista Muzeelor și Monumentelor
RRH	= Revue Roumaine d'Histoire
RSL	= Romanoslavica
RT	= Revista Teologică
SAI	= Studii și Articole de Istorie
SAO	= Studia et Acta Orientalia
SB	= Studia Balcanica
SCI	= Studii și Cercetări Istorice
SCIA	= Studii și Cercetări de Istoria Artei
SCIM	= Studii și Cercetări de Istorie Medie
SCN	= Studii și Cercetări de Numismatică
SCȘI	= Studii și Cercetări Științifice. Iași
SEER	= The Slavonic and East European Review
SJAN	= Serviciul Județean al Arhivelor Naționale
SMIM	= Studii și Materiale de Istorie Medie
SOF	= Süd Ost Forschungen, München
ST	= Studii Teologice
Studii	= Studii. Revistă de Istorie

SUBB	= Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai. Historia
TR	= Transylvanian Review
TV	= Teologie și Viață
UKB	= Urkundenbuch zur Geschichte der Deutschen in Siebenbürgen

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